

Project Report

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Implementation and Analysis of various Data Structures and Algorithms for rendering of Large Terrain Datasets

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Abstract

Digital and Web based maps are stuck at 2D mode for a long time. Also, various novel methodologies and instruments have been developed to collect huge amounts of good quality terrain data using technologies such as LiDAR, people now want to visualize these data in 3D formats. Also, with the increasing processing power of GPUs and CPUs, efficient processing and rendering 3D terrain data is now a problem that is looked upon by researchers all around the world. Visualizing large scale terrain information has a lot of application in today's world. From mapping the earth's terrain at places of interest to visualizing the terrain of other planets, efficient storing, processing and rendering of terrain data is becoming extremely important.

In this work, we study, implement and analyse different techniques and algorithms to build 3D meshes from DEMs (Digital Elevation Models) for terrain visualization. We also provide a detailed analysis and comparison of the different algorithms implemented and their respective advantages and limitations.

Introduction

Storing and rendering 3D terrains from terrain datasets has been an interesting problem for computer graphics researchers around the world. Many different data structures and algorithms have been developed over the years for efficient storage, processing and rendering of 3D terrain data. Terrain meshes can be realized in mainly 2 formats namely using Triangular Irregular Networks and in the Raster data format in the form of Quad trees.

The most popular algorithms for generating TIN's include Incremental Delaunay Triangulation, Divide and Conquer technique, Sweep-Hull technique, Bowyer Watson algorithm etc.

Similarly, popular algorithms following Quadtree approach include Restricted quadtree Triangulation, Quadtree surface maps, Continuous LOD rendering, Realtime optimally adapting meshes, etc.

Although, there may be many other formats for processing terrain data, we focus on the ones that are most popular. We selected 3 techniques for mesh generation and rendering, implemented them, analyzed them and presented a detailed comparison of these algorithms against each other.

The 3 techniques that we implemented and analyzed in this work are:

1. Incremental Delaunay Triangulation.
2. Simple Quadtree based LOD Terrain Triangulation.
3. Virtual Globe based Multi-resolution TIN surface modelling.

Then finally, we implemented Real time Optimally Adapting Meshes Algorithm.

All three of these techniques were implemented in **C++11**, visualized them using **matplotlib**, **OpenGL** and **CesiumJS** respectively and recorded, analysed and compared their Space and Time complexities. The Advantages and limitations of each of the above approaches have also been discussed.

Brief Descriptions

1. **DEMs:** Digital Elevation Models (basically a matrix of numbers) are a way to represent terrain data in the form of either Raster data (a grid of squares also known as height maps) or TIN's. DEMs could be acquired through multiple techniques such as photogrammetry, lidar, IfSAR, land surveying, etc. These are generally the starting point of any terrain visualization workflow.
2. **TINs:** A triangulated irregular network is a representation of a continuous surface consisting entirely of triangular facets used as a grid in primary elevation modelling. The vertices of these triangles consists of various information regarding the terrain like coordinates, heights, etc. It is basically a vector based representation of physical land surface, sea bottom, made up of irregularly distributed nodes and lines with 3 D coordinates (x,y,z) that are arranged in a network of non-overlapping triangles.
3. **Raster Data:** A raster data structure is based on a (usually rectangular, square-based) tessellation of the 2D plane into cells. Direct rendering of raster data is often much more costly than rendering TINs but it is easier to build regular raster tiles than TIN tiles.
4. **Quadtree:** A quadtree is a tree data structure in which each internal node has exactly four children. Quadtrees are the two-dimensional analog of octrees and are most often used to partition a two-dimensional space by recursively subdividing it into four quadrants or regions. The data associated with a leaf cell varies by application, but the leaf cell represents a unit of interesting spatial information.
5. **GIS:** A Geographic Information System (GIS) is a system designed to capture, store, manipulate, analyze, manage, and present spatial or geographic data. GIS applications are tools that allow users to create interactive queries (user-created searches), analyze spatial information, edit data in maps, and present the results of all these operations.

6. **GeoDatabases:** A geo-database is a database optimized for storing and querying spatial geographic data. These geodatabases can handle more complex structures such as 3D objects, topological coverages, linear networks and TINs.
7. **LiDAR:** Lidar (light detection and ranging) is a remote-sensing technique that uses laser light to densely sample the surface of the earth with x,y,z measurements. Lidar datasets produce mass point datasets that can be visualized and analyzed using terrain datasets.
8. **HeightMaps:** A heightmap or heightfield is a raster image used mainly as Discrete Global Grid in secondary elevation modelling. Each pixel store values, such as surface elevation data, for display in 3D computer graphics.

Proposed Approaches

1. Incremental Delaunay Triangulation for TIN based approach

Figure. Steps showing the process of Incremental Delaunay Triangulation

The most straightforward way of efficiently computing the Delaunay triangulation is to repeatedly add one vertex at a time, re-triangulating the affected parts of the graph. When a vertex v is added, we split in three the triangle that contains v , then we apply the flip algorithm. If done naively, this will take $O(n)$ time, we search through all the triangles to find the one that contains v , then we potentially flip away every triangle. Then the overall runtime is $O(n^2)$. If we insert the vertices in a random order, then overall the runtime time complexity can be brought down to $O(n \log n)$.

Algorithm Steps:

1. The first step of the algorithm is to create this *imaginary* triangle that encloses all the points of the set, inserting it as root in the tree and inserting it in the DCEL. This imaginary triangle idea is depicted below.

Figure. Boundary triangle formation. The initial step of Triangulation

2. The second step is a loop executed for all the remaining points of the set. This step is executed in several stages:
 - Locate the triangle that encloses the point.
 - Create three (or four) new triangles.
 - Update the DCEL and the tree with the new triangles.
 - Check if any edge is not a Delaunay edge and flip it if not.

3. This triangulation starts creating a triangle that has two imaginary points named P-1 and P-2. That means that this first triangle is also an imaginary face. Along the process, when splitting triangles, some of them will also be imaginary as they have one or two of the imaginary points as a vertex. Those faces are imaginary and that means they do not belong to the final triangulation. So, the triangles containing those faces need to be eliminated.

Figure. Final Triangulation

2. ROAM: Real time optimally adapting meshes

Real-time optimally adapting mesh (ROAM), is a continuous [level of detail algorithm](#) that optimizes terrain [meshes](#). It enables dynamic mesh representation based on Bin Trees. It uses triangle bintrees and the split and merge operations are used to maintain continuous meshes while adding and removing one vertex at a time. Animation of the splits and merges is

presented as a simple method for obtaining temporal continuity. On modern computers, sometimes it is more effective to send a small amount of unneeded polygons to the GPU, rather than burden the CPU with LOD (Level of Detail) calculations.

Algorithm Steps:

1. Height Map files are loaded into memory and associated with an instance of a Landscape class. Multiple Landscape objects may be linked to generate terrains of infinite size.
2. A new Landscape object parcels out sections of the loaded Height Map to new Patch class objects. The purpose of this step is two-fold:
 - a. The tree-based structures used for the rest of the algorithm expand RAM usage exponentially with depth, so keeping the areas small limits their depths.
 - b. Dynamic updates of the Height Field need a complete recalculation of the variance tree over the modified locations. Overly large Patches would be too slow to recompute in a real-time application.
3. Each Patch object is then called to create a mesh approximation (tessellation). The Patches employ a structure called a Binary Triangle Tree which stores implicit coordinates for the triangles that will be displayed on the screen (instead of explicit X,Y,Z coordinates). By storing the vertices in a logical manner, ROAM saves upwards of 36 bytes of RAM per triangle. Coordinates are calculated efficiently as part of the rendering step (below).
4. After tessellation, the engine traverses the Binary Triangle Tree created in the previous step. Leaf nodes in the tree represent triangles which need to be output to

the graphics pipeline. The triangle coordinates are calculated on the fly during the traversal.

Figure. Bin-Tree Split and Merge Operations

3. Virtual Globe based Multiresolution TIN Surface Modelling

Figure. The process of multi-resolution TIN pyramid construction.

The integration and visualization of geospatial data on a virtual globe is another significant strategy in understanding and analysis of the Earth surface processes. A high-accuracy multi-resolution TIN pyramid construction and visualization method for virtual globe was proposed by [6]. Firstly, it introduces the cartographic principles to formulize the level of detail (LOD) generation so that the TIN model in each layer is controlled with a data quality standard. A maximum z-tolerance algorithm is then used to iteratively construct the multi-resolution TIN pyramid. Moreover, the extracted landscape features are incorporated into each-layer TIN, thus preserving the topological structure of terrain surface at different levels. A virtual node (VN)-based approach is developed to seamlessly partition and discretize each triangulation layer into tiles, which can be organized and stored with a global quad-tree index. The experimental results showed that the proposed method can achieve an high-fidelity terrain representation, while producing a high quality underlying data that satisfies the demand for scientific analysis. This algorithm is also sometimes known as the Zemlya meshing algorithm.

Figure. The Virtual Node (VN) Structure

Algorithm Steps:

1. First, it repeatedly downsampled the original raster to create average values for lower zoom levels, all the way to zoom level 1.

2. Then it iterates over all the zoom levels in a top-down fashion, starting with zoom level 1. At each zoom level, we start with the mesh generated from the previous zoom level, then insert the average values at this zoom level using the same greedy insertion algorithm as in Terra.(From tin-terrain).
3. We iterate over all the zoom levels until we reach the final zoom level, which consists of points from the original raster.

Methodology

An overview of the workflow's followed by our choice of terrain rendering algorithms has been depicted below.

1.

Figure: Flowchart for terrain rendering using TINs.

2.

Figure. Flowchart for multi-resolution terrain rendering using Quadtrees or Virtual nodes.

Datasets:

1. We evaluated our algorithms on the data obtained from USGS (United States Geological Survey) websites. The data was in the form of DEMs. One such DEM model of a Crater Lake can be found [here](#). Crater Lake National Park DEMS covers 12 7.5-minute quadrangle maps and these 12 individual quads has been mosaicked together. The size of this DEM set was 103Mb.
2. Another dataset of heightmaps were used in the final ROAM algorithm implementation since ROAM algorithm requires height maps for generating LOD terrains. It can be downloaded from [here](#). The size of this dataset was nearly ~24Mb.

Implementation and Results:

The results obtained from the above 3 implementations are given below. The different approaches are compared with respect to Time complexity, Space complexity, Rendering Efficiency, etc.

Time Complexity for generating meshes comparisons:

Incremental Delaunay Triangulation	Quadtree based LOD algorithm	Virtual globe based multi-resolution algorithm
$O(N_2)$	$O(N\log N)$	$O(N\log N)$

Runtime Comparisons:

On a machine with an Intel i5 2.4 GHz Processor, 8 GB RAM and Intel IRIS Graphics of 1.5GB, with Tin-Terra Software and CesiumJS viewer,

1. Incremental Delaunay Triangulation took 10mins55sec to generate the mesh.
2. Generating mesh using Virtual Globe approach took 5mins9sec.
3. Generating a simple triangulated raster also took around 6mins.

We again mention that these are system specific durations, but the relative ratios will hold everywhere.

Space Complexity Comparisons:

Incremental Delaunay Triangulation algorithm	Quadtree based LOD algorithms	Virtual globe based multi-resolution algorithms
$O(N)$	$O(N^4)$	$\sim O(N)$

Talking a bit more about space complexities, space and compute requirements for TIN based algorithms are always high as they try to render the entire landscape in a single go. On the other hand, space complexity of LOD (Level of Detail) algorithms is small as only a small part of the terrain has to be rendered at a time. That's the reason, TIN algorithms don't perform well on machines with low compute and memory.

Our final implementation of ROAM (Realtime optimally adapting meshes) Algorithm implementation was compiled and ran on a x84_64 bit CentOS machine with 40 Intel(R) Xeon (R) Silver 4114 CPU @ 2.20GHZ, 64 GB RAM, 4TB HDD and an NVIDIA Quadro P4000 2GB GPU . OpenGL 3 was used for the rendering purpose.

The heightmap used was a 1024 x 1024 matrix. The rendering efficiency observed was between 60 and 61 fps.

Figure. Screenshot of ROAM Implementation

Figure. Screenshot of Incremental Delaunay Triangulation Implementation

Analysis, Advantages and Limitations:

1. Triangulated Irregular Networks are meshes that contain only vertices where they define meaningful change in surface height. In flat areas, where there is no extra data required, no vertices are added. To illustrate this, we can imagine a perfectly flat square. We can define this using two triangles and only four points, regardless of the resolution or area covered. By the same principle, we can define some areas almost perfectly with only a few points while for others we may need many more.

While, in the case of Quadtree based bintree raster structures, the frequency of the bin trees have to be uniform and hence there would be a lot of useless triangles that have to be rendered. This affects the FPS while rendering.

2. TINs maintain and provide more detailed rendering as their are more number of smaller triangles in places with high variability and detail. So sharp corners and edges are maintained very nicely in case Triangulated irregular networks.

While in the case of regular and uniform raster data format, the triangulations being totally uniform pose the problem of missing out sharp corners and edges and leading to lower detail in places that have very high variability.

3. Virtual globe based approach uses triangulations too, so its performance is almost similar to that of incremental delaunay triangulation approach.

Quadtree based LOD approaches
Outperform virtual globe approach in terms of rendering speed and efficiency.

4. The performance of Realtime optimally adapting meshing algorithm looks the best because of its interactive frame rates. This is mainly because, it uses Quadtree structures and partitioning into bin trees and merging back which doesn't incur much complexity.

But, in spite of its performance it still lacks in use cases which need perfect rendering of every of each and every detail of the terrain. This is again due to its uniform bin tree data structure.

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